

Investigation of property of silver complex solution with *p*-iodobenzenediazoaminoazobenzene by spectral correction technique

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Complexation between silver (Ag^+) and *p*-iodobenzenediazoaminoazobenzene (*p*-IBDA) has been investigated in alkaline solution. The surfactants, polyoxyethylene alcohol (OP) and sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate (SDBS) have been used because their micelles can improve the dissolution of the Ag-*p*-IBDA complex and increase the reaction sensitivity. Its true (not apparent) molar absorptivity is $\epsilon_{\text{Ag}(p\text{-IBDA})}^{480} = 3.42 \times 10^4$ in OP solution and $\epsilon_{\text{Ag}(p\text{-IBDA})}^{490} = 2.59 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in SDBS solution. The stability constants of the complex are 1.63×10^7 and 5.16×10^4 in OP and SDBS solutions, respectively.

The metal silver can form complexes with a lot of chromogenic agents, such as azo compounds^{1,2}, thio-ligands^{3,4}, acidic and basic dyes^{5,6}, porphyrin compounds⁷ and so on. The synthesis of the new ligand, *p*-iodobenzenediazoaminoazobenzene (*p*-IBDA) was carried out and the structure of the compound is given below :

The reaction between silver(I) and *p*-IBDA is sensitive in alkaline solution. We found that the surfactants, polyoxyethylene alcohol (OP) and sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate (SDBS) are helpful to improve the dissolution of complex and effective to increase the sensitivity of the complex reaction because the micelles will adsorb *p*-IBDA molecules then combine Ag^+ to form large molecule $\text{Ag}(p\text{-IBDA})(\text{OP})_n$ or $\text{Ag}(p\text{-IBDA})(\text{SDBS})_n$. Because of the absorption of excess of ligand, the spectral correction technique^{8,10} has been applied in the determination of properties of the reaction between Ag^+ and *p*-IBDA instead of the ordinary spectrophotometry, which was earlier applied to determine trace amounts of components^{9,10}. This method is accurate, simpler in operation and more acceptable in principle than the classical methods for example molar ratio¹¹, Yatzimirsky¹² and so on. Results show that complex $\text{Ag}(p\text{-IBDA})$ is formed in alkaline solution in presence of OP and SDBS having absorptivities 3.42×10^4 at 480 nm and $2.59 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 490 nm, and stability constants 1.63×10^7 and 5.16×10^4 , respectively.

Principle :

The following expression is developed for the determination of the real absorbance (A_c) of metal (M) complex (ML_γ) produced with a ligand (L),

$$A_c = \frac{\Delta A - \beta \Delta A'}{1 - \alpha \beta}$$

The symbols ΔA and $\Delta A'$ are the absorbances of the mixed solution of ML_γ and excess L measured at wavelengths λ_2 and λ_1 against the reagent blank, respectively. The coefficients α and β are correction factors and they are able to be measured from only ML_γ solution and L solution then computed as

$$\alpha = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{ML}_\gamma}^{\lambda_1}}{\epsilon_{\text{ML}_\gamma}^{\lambda_2}}$$

and

$$\beta = \frac{\epsilon_L^{\lambda_2}}{\epsilon_L^{\lambda_1}}$$

Here, the terms $\epsilon_{\text{ML}_\gamma}^{\lambda_1}$, $\epsilon_{\text{ML}_\gamma}^{\lambda_2}$, $\epsilon_L^{\lambda_1}$ and $\epsilon_L^{\lambda_2}$ are the molar absorptivities of ML_γ and L at wavelengths λ_1 and λ_2 , respectively. The molar ratio (γ') of effective L to M in their reaction may be expressed as

$$\gamma' = \eta \times \frac{C_L}{C_M}$$

where,

$$\eta = \frac{\alpha \Delta A - \Delta A'}{(1 - \alpha \beta) A_0'}$$

Here, η indicates the reacted percentage of L and η the cell thickness (cm), C_M and C_L are the concentrations (mol dm^{-3}) of M and L in the beginning and A_0' is the absorbance of the blank reagent measured at wavelength λ_1 . If γ' reaches maximum and remains constant, it is thought that $\gamma = \gamma'$, where γ is a natural number and it is the

stoichiometric ratio of the complex produced. In addition, the following expression was established for the stepwise stability constant (K_n) of complex ML_γ from the reaction : $ML_{n-1} + L \rightleftharpoons ML_n$. For this purpose, an M-L solution must be prepared to form the complex ratio γ' between $(n-1)$ and n and studied successively,

$$K_n = \frac{\gamma' + 1 - n}{(n - \gamma')(C_L - \gamma' C_M)}$$

From each K_n the cumulative constant (K) of complex ML_γ is calculated from the expression, $K = K_1 \times K_2 \times \dots \times K_n \dots \times K_\gamma$.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra of *p*-IBDA and its Ag^+ complex : The absorption spectra of *p*-IBDA and silver-*p*-IBDA solutions at pH 12 are shown in Fig. 1. From curves 1-3, 2-3 and 3-3, we observe that the spectra in the presence of OP (curve 1-3) and SDBS (curve 2-3) give out the high peak and valley absorption. Therefore, the two surfactants, OP

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of *p*-IBDA and its Ag^+ reaction solutions at pH 12 : (1) in presence of OP, (2) in presence of SDBS, (3) in presence of CTMAB; (1) *p*-IBDA (0.80 μ mol) solution against water, (2) Ag^+ (200 μ g)-*p*-IBDA (0.40 μ mol) complex solution (*p*-IBDA is zero excess) against water, (3) Ag^+ (40 μ g)-*p*-IBDA (0.80 μ mol) reaction solution against reagent blank.

and SDBS were used in the present work. By comparing curves 1-1 and 1-2, the sensitive absorption of *p*-IBDA solution is located at 540 nm and that of Ag -*p*-IBDA complex solution at <450 nm in presence of OP. The difference of two wavelengths is about 90 nm. Similarly, from curves 2-1 and 2-2, the sensitive absorption of *p*-IBDA solution is located at 490 nm and that of Ag -*p*-IBDA complex solution at 410 nm in presence of SDBS. The difference of two wavelengths is 80 nm. However, we should select working wavelengths (peak at λ_2 and valley at λ_1) from curves 1-3 and 2-3 so as to give the highest absorbance. Results are shown in Table 1. From curves 1-2 and 1-1, we calculate α and β for Ag -*p*-IBDA-OP system at pH 12, respectively.

Similarly, from curves 2-2 and 2-1, α and β values are worked out for Ag -*p*-IBDA-SDBS system. The data are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Selection of work wavelengths and calculation of α and β from absorption spectra of *p*-IBDA and its Ag^+ complex solutions at pH 12

Reaction system	Work wavelengths, nm		Correction coefficients	
	λ_1	λ_2	α	β
Ag - <i>p</i> -IBDA-OP	550	480	0.205	0.861
Ag - <i>p</i> -IBDA-SDBS	410	490	0.474	0.212

Effect of *p*-IBDA concentration : By varying the addition of *p*-IBDA solution, the effect on absorption of each of silver (40 μ g) solutions is shown in Fig. 2. From the curves it is revealed that the positive and negative absorptions

Fig. 2. Effect of addition of *p*-IBDA solution on absorption of Ag^+ (40 μ g)-*p*-IBDA solution at pH 12 : (1-1) in presence of OP at 480 nm, (2-1) in presence of SDBS at 490 nm, (1-2) in presence of OP at 550 nm, (2-2) in presence of SDBS at 410 nm

both approach maximum when the addition of *p*-IBDA solution is over 2.0 ml. Calculated A_c of the complex and its complexation ratio (γ') of *p*-INDA to Ag^+ at various additions of *p*-IBDA solution are shown in Fig. 3. From maximal A_c of curves 1-1 and 2-1, the real molar absorptivity of complex is calculated as followed : $\epsilon_{Ag^+-IBDA}^{480} = 3.42 \times 10^4$

Fig. 3. Effect of addition of *p*-IBDA solution on A_c (curves x-1) of Ag^+ (40 μ g)-*p*-IBDA complex solution and γ' (curves x-2) of *p*-IBDA to Ag : (1) in presence OP at 480 nm, (2) in presence of SDBS at 490 nm.

in the presence of OP and $\epsilon_{Ag(p-IBDA)}^{490} = 2.59 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the presence of SDBS both at pH 12. However, from curves 1-2 and 2-2 (Fig. 2) its apparent absorptivity is found only 2.11×10^4 and $1.85 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. From curves 1-2 and 2-2 (Fig. 3), we observed that the maximum of γ is 1. Therefore, the complex may be expressed as $Ag(p-IBDA)$.

Effect of color-developed time : The positive and negative absorptions of silver ($40 \mu\text{g}$)-*p*-IBDA solution were measured at various color-developed time. Then A_c of solution was calculated according to the equation (vide Principle) and its curves are shown in Fig. 4. We observed that in both the cases A_c approaches to maximum at time be-

Fig. 4. Effect of time on A_c of Ag^+ ($40 \mu\text{g}$)-*p*-IBDA ($0.80 \mu\text{mol}$) complex solution at pH 12 : (1) in presence of OP at 480 nm, (2) in presence of SDBS at 490 nm.

tween 5 and 20 min. When the time is over 20 min, the absorbance begins to decrease slowly. Therefore, the reaction solution had to be measured in 20 min.

Effect of pH : By varying pH of the solutions in the presence of OP and SDBS, the absorbance of each solution was measured at two wavelengths. Results are shown in Fig. 5. In both the reactions the absorption (A_c) of the com-

Fig. 5. Effect of pH on A_c of Ag^+ ($40 \mu\text{g}$)-*p*-IBDA ($0.80 \mu\text{mol}$) complex solution : (1) in presence of OP at 480 nm, (2) in presence of SDBS at 490 nm.

plex increases rapidly when pH of solution of greater than 10. The highest absorption of complex is observed at pH >12. Therefore, the reaction between Ag^+ and *p*-IBDA is sensitive only in alkaline solution.

Effect of addition of 5% surfactants : By varying the addition of 5% OP and SDBS, the positive and negative absorptions of the reaction solution were measured (Fig. 6). The real absorbance is found to approach to maximum at

Fig. 6. Effect of addition of OP and SDBS solution on A_c of Ag^+ ($40 \mu\text{g}$)-*p*-IBDA ($0.80 \mu\text{mol}$) complex solution at pH 12 : (1) in presence of OP at 480 nm, (2) in presence of SDBS at 490 nm.

1.0–2.0 ml addition of 5% OP or SDBS, where a lot of micelles are formed in solution because the concentration of the surfactants is over CMC. These micelles adsorb *p*-IBDA molecules, then Ag^+ is combined with the adsorbed *p*-IBDA to form large molecule $Ag(p-IBDA)(OP)_n$ or $Ag(p-IBDA)(SDBS)_n$ (n indicates the total numbers of OP or SDBS molecules in a micelle). Therefore, OP and SDBS can improve the dissolution of complex in alkaline solution and increase the reaction sensitivity.

Determination of stability constant (K) : The following two solutions have been used for the calculation of step-wise and cumulative stability constant of complexes : $0.40 \mu\text{mol}/25 \text{ ml } Ag^+$ with $0.40 \mu\text{mol}/25 \text{ ml } p-IBDA$ in OP solution and $0.40 \mu\text{mol}/25 \text{ ml } Ag^+$ with $0.20 \mu\text{mol}/25 \text{ ml } p-IBDA$ in SDBS solution. The 1st-step stability constant (equal to cumulative that) of the complex was calculated (Table 2). We find that complex formed in presence of OP is much more stable than that formed in presence of SDBS. The former reaction should be more useful than the latter in the determination of trace silver or other applications. Therefore, in a complex solution, not only ionic strength and temperature affect its stability but also the different additives such as surfactants would give different results.

Conclusion : The reaction between Ag^+ and *p*-IBDA at pH 12 forms complex whose composition ratio is $Ag : p-IBDA = 1 : 1$. Because *p*-IBDA and $Ag-p-IBDA$ complex are insoluble in alkaline solution, OP and SDBS are helpful

to improve their dissolution and the reaction's sensitivity. This investigation has worked out clearly the property factors of Ag-*p*-IBDA complex solution at pH 12 by using the

Table 2. Determination of the stability constant of Ag-*p*-IBDA complex in OP and SDBS presence at pH 12

Ionic strength = 0.01 M, temp. = 20°

Reaction system	Absorbances		Complex ratio γ'	Stability constant $K (K = K_1)$
	λ_1	λ_2		
Ag- <i>p</i> -IBDA-OP	-0.186	0.036	0.940	1.63×10^7
	-0.189	0.038	0.940	1.63×10^7
	mean : 1.63×10^7			
Ag- <i>p</i> -IBDA-SDBS	-0.114	0.048	0.203	5.36×10^4
	-0.112	0.047	0.195	4.96×10^4
	-0.118	0.045	0.199	5.16×10^4
	mean : 5.16×10^4			

spectral correction spectrophotometry. This technique is useful in the determination of properties of metal complexes and has prospect for application in spectrophotometry, spectrofluorometry, resonance light scattering etc.

Experimental

Absorption spectra were measured on a Shimadzu UV-265 spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm cell. A $0.400 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$ *p*-IBDA solution was prepared in acetone (Shanghai Reagents) and stored in dark bottle at $<5^\circ$. A 100.0 mg dm^{-3} silver solution was prepared from silver nitrate (A.R., Shanghai Reagents) and a 10.0 mg dm^{-3} Ag working solu-

tion was prepared prior to experimentation. A 10% KOH was used to adjust the pH at 12 of the experimental solution. 5% (w/v) solutions of the surfactants OP (Shanghai OReagents) and SDBS (Shanghai Reagents) were prepared.

Procedure : To silver solution ($40 \mu\text{g Ag}^+$) were added the surfactant solution (1 ml) and varying amount of *p*-IBDA solution separately and the volume was made up to 25 ml with water and mixed well. Then between 10 and 20 min, the absorbances at two wavelengths (Table 1) were measured against the reagent blank and water reference.

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